

Searsia lancea

Karee

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Group: Eudicot

Size: Up to 8 meters.

Distribution:

Searsia lancea is widespread across southern Africa, including South Africa, Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Lesotho, and Eswatini. In South Africa, it occurs in all provinces and is common in semi-arid regions, especially along riverbanks, savannas, and disturbed areas.

Importance:

Searsia lancea is a hardy, fast-growing indigenous tree important for dryland ecosystems and urban greening due to its resilience. Despite its ecological value and widespread use, genomic resources are lacking, and genome sequencing would support conservation, restoration, and climate adaptation research.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 100.94 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 19.61 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.42 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.6% [Single: 94.1%, Duplicated: 4.5%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 1 049.17 kilobases

Contig number: 1 667

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